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Career Maturity as Predictors of Job Involvement among Guidance Counsellors in Anambra State Public Secondary Schools

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Abstract

The study investigated career maturity as predictors of job involvement among counsellors in Anambra state public secondary schools. Two research questions guided the study, correlational research design was adopted for the study. The population for the study consisted of 122 professional Guidance Counsellors from 268 public secondary schools in Anambra State. Census sampling method was used. This approach was adopted due to the relatively small population on size, allowing for a comprehensive examination of the phenomenon under study. Two instruments were adopted by the researcher titled Career Maturity Inventory (CMI) developed by Crites (1961), and Job Involvement Scale (JIS) developed by Lodahi Kejner (1965). The instruments were face validated by three experts. The reliability was established using cronbach Alpha. The result gave a coefficient value of 0.70 for career maturity Inventory and 0.90 for Job involvement scale. The data were collected by the researcher with the help of three research assistants who were properly briefed on how to administer and retrieve copies of the instrument. The data were analyzed using simple regression statistic and multiple regression analysis. The findings of the study revealed that there was a significant prediction of job involvement among guidance counsellors by career maturity in public secondary schools in Anambra state. The study also found that male and female career maturity significantly predicted male and female job involvement among guidance counsellors in public secondary schools in Anambra state. Based on the above findings, the researcher recommended among others that the ministry of education should organize regular training and workshops to enhance guidance counsellors' career maturity for better job performance. This study has revealed the extent to which individual career preparedness impacts counsellor's involvement, offering a model for future studies and training design.

Keywords: Career maturity, job involvement, guidance counsellors, public secondary schools.

INTRODUCTION

In the dynamic and ever-evolving world of work, the role of employees extends beyond were task execution. Their psychological identification with their roles, enthusiasm, and willingness to go the extra mail have become essential for institutional success. This concept, known as job involvement, reflects how deeply individuals engage with their work, how important they perceive it to be in their lives, and the extent to which it influences their identity and satisfaction in the context of guidance counsellors in educational institutions, job involvement is critical, as their effectiveness directly impacts students' development, career decisions, and emotional well-being.

Kanugo (2018), job involvement is a cognitive state of identification with one's job which is characterized by a sense of psychological attachment to the job and a feeling of being fully engaged in the job. These employees join the organization with certain motives which they equally hope to realize while performing their various tasks in the organization. Guidance counsellors in public secondary schools face several challenges that affect their job involvement, including high work loads that leads to burnout, limited resources that hinder effective support, and inadequate administrative backing. Saks (2016), described job involvement as the strict cognitive evaluation of one's job and how it pertains to whom that person is as an individual. He also noted that highly job involved individual's make the job a central part of their personal character. It shows the degree to which an individual is personally involved with his/her job. He further stated that job involvement is one's motivated orientation to having the job in which they are engaged. According to Omoniyi and Adedapo (2015) job involvement is the degree to which an employee is engaged in and enthusiastic about performing his/her job. It describes the process of internalizing the importance of work based on individual formed opinion about one's career and it depicts a function of the level of satisfaction which an individual can derive on it by helping to meet certain desires. Highly job involved individuals make the job a central part of their personal character.

The researcher defined job involvement as the degree of performance of one's task or job. Job involvement of guidance counsellor is referred to as the degree of which the guidance counsellors perform their duties. In other words, the involvement of the guidance counsellors may be adequate or unsatisfactory. In most cases, the level of the guidance counsellors' involvement is measured by the students performance in school. A mature professional is more likely to be confident in their role, better equipped to handle job responsibilities, and more nailing to engage fully in their career. In the content of education, counsellors with high career maturity are likely to experience stronger job involvement because they view their role as a meaningful and integral part of their professional identity.

Career maturity is a vital aspect of personal growth. In the educational sector, particularly among guidance counsellors, career maturity plays a critical role in shaping their effectiveness, satisfaction, and overall job performance. Career maturity reflects an individual's readiness and ability to make informed, realistic and appropriate career decisions at various stages of life. It also determine how well a person adapts to career tasks, roles and challenges.

Anderson and Vandelely (2016) noted that two basic factors must come together when people deal with career issues. One factor is the self and represents the career identity of the human being. The dimension of self is placed along the top lines of the diamond indicates that primary task of realizing aspects of one's self as related to career development. For example, finding a satisfying career requires an understanding one's personality. Knowing one's interest and values can serve as important indicator for finding work expressive of one's career self concept. The self can also find outlets for abilities through work and can use career performance for achievement motivation. The second factor is the world of work which is placed along the bottom line of the diamond. The word of work includes all the external factors that must be taken into account when making career decisions, such factors includes requirement and specifications of occupation, economic realities, new career opportunity among others.

Salami (2018) described career maturity as one's ability to successfully cope with vocational development task with such as crystallization, specifying and implementing career choice that are encountered across the development continuum from exploration stage through withdrawal. As a construct, it represents a repertoire of coping behaviours towards career related events encountered at various life stages.

Walker (2020) defined career maturity as the individual's readiness to cope with the developmental tasks with which he or she is confronted because of his or her biological and social developments and because of society's expectation of people who have reached that stage of development.

The researcher defined career maturity as physical, psychological, emotional, social and mental readiness of a person to effectively deal with career related issues. It encompasses both cognitive and affective components. Such as decision-making abilities, career planning, self-awareness, and understanding of the world of work. In the context of guidance counsellors, career maturity is crucial. Counsellors with high career maturity are not only more capable of managing their own professional lives but are also better

equipped to guide students through their own career journeys. They can set clear goals, evaluate career options critically and take proactive steps towards professional development. Career maturity also correlates positively with job involvement and professional commitment. A mature guidance counselor is more likely to engage actively in their work, take initiative in school programs, and serve as a role model for students navigating career choices.

Career maturity provides a foundation for effective career behaviour, long-term success, and personal fulfillment. It is a quality that can be nurtured through training, mentorship, and reflective practices, especially among education professionals such as guidance counsellors.

Statement of the Problem

Obviously, many guidance counsellors in public secondary schools show different levels of commitment to their work. This may be linked to their career maturity, their ability to make sound career decisions and grow professionally. Low career maturity could lead to poor job involvement, affecting their performance. To enhance career maturity among guidance counsellors and improve job involvement, the government should implement: professional development and training for guidance counsellors to boost career maturity. Introduce mentorship programs to guide less experienced counsellors, encourage school management to support and recognize counsellors' efforts to enhance job commitment. However, there is little research on how career maturity job involvement, influences especially among counsellors in Anambra state. This study aims to fill that gap.

Specifically, the study investigated

1. Examine the predictive value of career maturity of guidance counsellors in public secondary schools.
2. Determine the predictive value on job involvement guidance counsellors in public secondary schools in Anambra state.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. What is the predictive value of career maturity of guidance counsellors in public secondary school in Anambra state
2. What is the predictive value of job involvement of male and female guidance counsellors in public secondary schools in Anambra state.

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. Career maturity would not significantly predict job involvement of guidance counsellors in public secondary schools in Anambra state.
2. Career maturity would not significantly predict job involvement of male and female guidance counsellors in public secondary schools in Anambra state.

RESEARCH METHODS

Research Design

The study adopted a correlational research design aimed at determining the relationship between career maturity and job involvement among guidance counsellors in public secondary schools. A correlational design seeks to establish the degree of relationship that exists between two or more variables. Nworgu (2017) noted that correlational design indicates the direction and magnitude of the relationship between the variables of the study. The correlational design is considered appropriate for the study because it seeks to predict the relationship among the variables: job involvement and career maturity of public secondary school guidance counsellors in Anambra state public secondary schools.

The study was carried out in 268 secondary schools in Anambra state. The population of the study comprised 122 professional guidance counsellors comprising male and females in urban and rural base schools from 268 public secondary schools in Anambra state. Source: Planning, research and statistics department, post primary school service commission Awka, 2016)

The sample size for this study consisted of 122 professional guidance counsellors comprising male and female in urban and rural base schools from 268 public secondary schools in Anambra state. The sample

size for this study consisted of 122 professional guidance counsellors (male and female) drawn from the population of the study, using census sampling. This approach was adopted due to the relatively small population on size, allowing for a comprehensive examination of the phenomenon under study.

The instrument contained three sections; A B and C. To ascertain the face validity of the instrument, the title of the study, purpose of the study, research questions, hypotheses as well as copies of the questionnaire were given to three experts, two were lecturers in Guidance and counselling and one in measurement and evaluation, all in the department of Educational Foundations, faculty of Education, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu university, Igbariam campus. These experts were requested to scrutinize the items in terms of content coverage, clarity and appropriateness of the language and relatedness of the items to research questions and hypotheses. The validities made some corrections like: indicate the sources of your instruments, change statement items to item statement, increase the number of your hypotheses. The comments and suggestions by validates were reflected before the final production of the instrument. The instrument was trial-tested on a representative sample of 30 Guidance counsellors randomly selected from 15 public secondary schools in Enugu state. The state was chosen for trial-tested because both states share the same educational characteristics.

The scores obtained were analyzed to determine the internal consistency of the items. This was done using cronbach Alpha method. The reliability co-efficient values of 0.70 for career maturity inventory, and 0.90 for job involvement scale. These reliability co-efficient were considered high because they fell within high reliability indices as directed by Creswell (2014) in the 0.00- 0.20 is very low, 0.21-0.40 is low, 0.41-0.60 moderate, 0.61-0.80 is high, while 0.81-1.00 is very high. The researcher administered the instruments to the respondents with the help of three research assistants who were properly briefed on how to administer the instrument. The researcher and the assistants administered copies of the instrument on the guidance counsellors at their various schools, using direct administration and retrieval method. The completed copies were collected on the spot and follow up visits were made where the respondents did not submit on the spot. The distribution and collection of the copies of the questionnaire lasted for three weeks. At the end of the collection process, out of 122 copies of the questionnaire distributed, two were not properly filled. The researcher used 120 copies of questionnaire for data analysis representing 98 percent.

Method of Data Analysis

Simple regression statistics was used to answer question 1-2, regression nalaysis of anova (ANOVA) test of significance was used to test hypotheses 1-2, hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 27 was used for data analysis.

Muijis in Cohen et al (2007) suggestion for assessing teh goodness of fit of regression model using squared regression co-efficient (R2) and Beta weights (β) was adopted in this study for data analysis for R2.

0.00	-	0.01	weak fit
0.01	-	0.03	modest fit
0.03	-	0.05	moderate fit
>0.05	-		strong fit

For Beta Weighting (B)

0.00	-	0.01	weak effect
0.01	-	0.03	modest effect
0.03	-	0.05	moderate effect
>0.05	-		Strong effect

For the hypotheses, where the obtained probability value (P-value) is equal or less than 0.05, the null hypotheses was rejected. But where the obtained P-value is greater than 0.05, the null hypotheses was not rejected.

PRESENTATION OF RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What is the predictive value of career maturity on job involvement of guidance counsellors in public secondary schools in Anambra State?*

Table 1: Simple Regression analysis for career maturity on job involvement of guidance counsellors.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R ²	SE of Estimate	Change Statistics		df ₁	df ₂	Sig F Change
					R ² Change	F Change			
1	0.368 ^a	0.135	0.127	7.026	0.135	9.124	1	118	0.003

a. predictors: (constant), career maturity.

Table 1 revealed the regression analysis for the variation on job involvement of guidance counsellors in public secondary schools in Anambra State that was predicted by career maturity.

The result revealed that when the responses of respondents on career maturity were correlated with job involvement, a correlation coefficient (R) of 0.368 with associated coefficient of determination (R²) of 0.135 were obtained. This coefficient of determination (R²) of 0.135 depicted that 13.5% variation of job involvement can be predicted by career maturity in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Question 2: *What is the predictive value of career maturity on job involvement of male and female guidance counsellors in public secondary schools in Anambra state?*

Table 2: Simple regression analysis of career maturity predicting job involvement of male and female guidance counsellors.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R ²	SE of Estimate	Change Statistics		df ₁	df ₂	Sig F Change	
					R ² Change	F Change				
1	Male	.246 ^a	0.060	0.041	7.261	0.060	3.089	1	48	0.085
	Female	0.255 ^a	0.051	0.037	7.158	0.051	3.635	1	68	0.061

a. predictors: (constant), male career maturity.

a. predictors: (constant), female career maturity.

Table 2 showed the regression analysis for the amount of variation in male and female job involvement of guidance counsellors in public secondary schools in Anambra State that was predicted by career maturity.

The result showed that when the responses of respondents on male career maturity were correlated with male job involvement, a correlation coefficient (R) of 0.246 with associated coefficient of determination (R²) of 0.060 were obtained. This coefficient of determination (R²) of 0.060 indicated that 6.0% variation in male job involvement could be predicted by male career maturity.

In the same vein, when the responses of respondents on female career maturity were correlated with female job involvement, a correlation coefficient (R) of 0.225 with associated coefficient of determination (R²) of 0.051 were obtained. This coefficient of determination (R²) of 0.051 indicated that 5.1% variation in female job involvement could be predicted by female career maturity.

Summary of Findings

From the analysis and interpretation of result, the following findings emerged.

- 13.5% variation of job involvement among guidance counsellors can be predicted by career maturity. Nevertheless, the study deduced that there was a significant prediction of job involvement among guidance counsellors by career maturity in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
- 6.0% variation in male job involvement among male guidance counsellors can be predicted by male career maturity while 5.1% variation in female job involvement among female guidance counsellors can be predicted by female career maturity. Despite that, male and female career maturity did not

significantly predict male and female job involvement among guidance counsellors in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of the study as revealed in Table 1 indicates a moderate level of career maturity and a high level of job involvement among guidance counsellors. Career maturity significantly predicts job involvement among guidance counsellors in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This means that guidance counsellors who exhibited greater career maturity tend to show higher levels of commitment, motivation and participation in their job roles within the school system. These counsellors are likely more confident in their professional responsibilities and more proactive in performing their duties. The finding supports the assumptions of trait and factor theory by Frank Parson, which emphasizes that individuals who attain career maturity demonstrate readiness to handle career related tasks and challenges, resulting in higher job satisfaction and involvement. It also aligns with Bandura's Concept of self-regulation, where matured career individuals are better at setting and achieving career goals. Enhancing career maturity through professional development and career interventions can improve job involvement and effectiveness. This findings is not surprising, as many guidance counsellors usually exhibit adequate mastery of knowledge and attitudinal components appropriate for counselling profession. In most cases, they do this without considering the positive influence of the career maturity on their professions. However, this finding collaborated with Adio and Popoola (2020) who found a significant prediction on career commitment of librarians in carrying out their professional duties. The result aligns with the scholar that career maturity enhances professions identity, decision-making and clarity of purpose, which are essential for sustained job involvement. Counsellor with high career maturity are likely to understand their responsibilities better, plan their work effectively and show more dedication to guiding students, thus increasing their psychological and emotional investment in their job. Supported by Adio and Popoola 2020 which established a positive relationship between career development and work place involvement. It suggests that when counsellors are clear about their career goals and feel competent in their roles, they are more to perform optimally and remain committed. In the context of Anambra State where school guidance counsellors face challenges such as limited resources and high students' populations, those with high career maturity may better cope, stay motivated, and contribute meaningfully to student support services. The result of the null hypothesis reveal that career maturity would not significantly predict job involvement among guidance counsellors in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This finding is also supported by Adio and Popoola (2020) who found that the level of career maturity and self-efficacy determines the level of professionalism and commitment of the workers to their job. No wonder Ohizu and Okoye (2016) observed that career commitment is the same thing as job involvement which can be influenced by achievement, motivation and work value orientation.

The findings of the study in Table 2 agrees with Maropanabi (2014) who found no significant variation in male and female career maturity. In line with the hypothesis tested, it was revealed that career maturity will not significantly predict job involvement among male and female guidance counsellors in public secondary schools in Anambra State. It has also been reported that male do not seem to have interest in showing their career maturity as much as the female.

It still seem to be barriers for men to show their competence fully, and for them to admit that they have little interest in career maturity. Male who are interested in career Decision-making ability can also have the problem with lack of motivation, it becomes more difficult to reflect over what you are doing and to develop more knowledge. No wonder, most male guidance counsellors engage in career support, professional networking for their professional achievement. On the surface female are still the professional builders and competent ones. Female to a greater extent have access to new opportunities and challenges and it is more common for female than male to have lifetime career satisfaction and fulfillment. It has also been reported that female show more positive attitude towards career maturity than male. This is not in consonance with Almiskry, Baker and Mohammed (2019) who found a significant differences in career maturity on job involvement of male and female guidance counsellors in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings and discussions, these conclusions were drawn; career maturity were found to be important factors in determining the level of job involvement of guidance counsellors in public secondary schools in Anambra State. In other words, guidance counselors with high career maturity and high self efficacy will perform better than those with low career maturity. Based on these findings, it was concluded that there was a predictive career maturity on Job involvement among guidance counsellors in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. The ministry of education should organize regular training and workshops to enhance guidance counsellors' career maturity for better job performance
2. School administrators should encourage continuous career planning and personal development among counsellors to sustain their engagement in the job.
3. Equal opportunity and support should be given to both male and female counsellors to enhance their job involvement irrespective of career maturity differences.

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